

PHYSIOLOGICAL MECHANISMS OF DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL QUALITIES

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Abstract. *Exercise creates mechanisms for the body to adapt to physical loads. Regular exercise increases the body's functional capacity. This can be explained by the effect of exercise on individual physiological parameters, i.e., the body's adaptation to physical loads, as a result of comparing changes in the physiological performance of trained and non-exercised people at rest, under the influence of standard and maximum physical loads.*

Keywords: *speed, endurance, muscle strength, absolute strength, relative strength, myofibrils, hypertrophy, ATF, creatine phosphate, agility, flexibility.*

Introduction. Systematic muscle work of the body leads to the gradual development of adaptation processes, ultimately affects all organs and systems, providing an opportunity to perform high-powered and long-lasting physical work. Adaptation to systematic muscle activity is connected with regulatory processes and coordination of functions, and occurs at the level of molecules (structural and enzyme proteins), cellular structures (nucleus, mitochondria, etc.), cells, tissues, organs and organisms. Such a wide range of adaptive changes - from the molecule to the whole organ or system - is reflected in the morphological, physiological, biochemical, and functional properties of all tissues and organs of the physically trained organism. In order to produce such adaptive changes in muscles or other tissues and organs, it is necessary to apply repeated physical loads.

Research methodology. Metabolic changes in an exercised organism differ from those in an unexercised organism in three main ways:

1. An increase in the reserve of energy resources in skeletal muscles and other tissues and organs;
2. Expanding the potential capacity of enzymatic systems;
3. Improvement of control mechanisms of substance and energy exchange through nervous and endocrine systems.

Under the influence of systematic training, changes in the physiological mechanisms developing physical qualities are observed in athletes.

Improving the training of athletes in future sports:

- Athlete characteristics;
- Energy reserves;
- Selecting athletes should focus on efficiency improvements based on genetic predisposition assessment.

Analysis and results. Sports activities, including physical training, are characterized by certain quality indicators. The main physical qualities include muscle strength, speed, endurance, agility and flexibility [1].

Force is calculated as the product of mass and acceleration, and muscle strength is determined by muscle tension, which depends primarily on muscle structure, biochemical processes during contraction, and physiological factors. The thicker the muscle, the greater its

cross-section, leading to increased contraction and force output. Muscle strength is measured by the force generated at maximum tension, observed in isometric mode or under maximum load.

Maximum tension during isometric contraction results from muscle fiber involvement. This observed force is known as the muscle's maximum force, dependent on both fiber count and muscle cross-section. The cross-section of a muscle relative to its length is termed the anatomical cross-section. The ratio of maximum strength to anatomical cross-section is called relative strength. The cross-section of muscle fiber length is the physiological cross-section, and the ratio of maximum strength to physiological cross-section is absolute muscle strength, expressed in kg [2]. The muscles with feather-shaped fibers have the greatest strength, followed by fusiform, and finally, muscles with parallel fibers. In addition, the strength of the muscle depends on its functional state, working conditions, characteristics of nerve impulses to the muscle. Muscle strength increases with exercise and decreases with hunger and fatigue.

The heaviest load an athlete can lift is termed their voluntary maximum strength. However, the combination of high-speed muscle contractions with maximal strength, especially over short distances, results in high performance. Not all fibers in muscle groups performing a task are activated to produce voluntary maximal force. That is why the maximum voluntary force is much less than the absolute force of the muscle. The difference between the maximum voluntary force and the absolute force of the muscle is called the strength deficit. Strength deficits are higher in non-athletes than in highly skilled athletes. Regular exercise in sports activities that develop strength (lifting weights, overcoming external resistance) leads to an increase in voluntary maximal strength. As a result, the difference between voluntary maximum strength and absolute strength decreases, that is, the strength deficit decreases, and muscle strength increases. The factors determining the maximum voluntary muscle strength can be divided into 2 groups [2].

1. Peripheral factors (muscle).
2. Central factors (nerve).

Peripheral factors affecting muscle strength include the number of muscle fibers involved in muscle contraction, the ratio of the type of muscle fibers (fast-twitch, slow-twitch), and the length of the muscle before contraction. Central factors include nerve centers that control the work of muscles and ensure their coordination.

An increase in muscle cross-section as a result of regular exercise is called active hypertrophy. In people with hypertrophied muscles, the mass of muscle tissue increases. In such athletes, body muscles can make up 50% of body weight. Hypertrophy caused by physical work is divided into two types.

1. Sarcoplasmic hypertrophy
2. Myofibrillar hypertrophy

Sarcoplasmic hypertrophy occurs mainly due to an increase in muscle protoplasm, which results in an increase in muscle strength. In sarcoplasmic hypertrophy, muscle thickening is due to an increase in substances such as proteins, glycogen, non-nitrogenous substances, ATP, creatine phosphate, and myoglobin, which do not participate in muscle contraction [3,11].

In myofibrillar working hypertrophy, the part that ensures the contraction of the muscle is due to the increase in the number and size of myofibrils. The absolute strength of the muscle is also greatly increased. However, it should be remembered that muscle strength depends more on the genetic factors than anything else, but the development of this ability, inherited ability, is realized through exercise.

Psychophysiological mechanisms of muscle strength gain depend on changes in functional state (wakefulness, drowsiness, exhaustion), motivations and emotions that enhance the sympathetic and hormonal effects through biorhythms involving the pituitary gland, adrenal glands, and gonads.

Morphological and biochemical changes that occur in muscle fibers under the influence of various types of training compared to those without training (according to I.K. Proskurina, 2001)

Parameters	Exercises		
	Endurance oriented	Speed	Strength training
Relative muscle mass as a % of body mass	9	32	30
Thickness of muscle fibers	0	24	30
Number of mitochondria per unit area	60	30	-
Myofibrillar proteins	7	63	68
Myoglobin	40	58	53
Creatine phosphate	10	20	-

Male sex hormones (androgens), which increase the synthesis of contractile proteins in skeletal muscles, play an important role in the development of strength. They are 10 times more prevalent in men than in women. This is why exercise is more effective in male athletes compared to female athletes at the same training loads [4].

Quickness, which is one of the physical qualities, is expressed by the time of execution of the movement, and it develops when physical exercises are performed at high speed.

From a physiological point of view, the speed of movement mainly depends on the following factors:

1. Excitability of the motor apparatus, that is, the latent period.
2. The time of muscle contraction and relaxation.
3. Lability of the neuromuscular tissue involved in a particular movement.

Speed development is important for sprinters and speed-power athletes because the faster an athlete starts, the faster they can cover the distance. Factors such as the type of neuro-muscular movement units, movement coordination, and the rate of energy generation in muscles play a role in high-speed execution of movement. The ratio of fast-twitch or slow-twitch motor units in the execution of a movement affects the speed of the movement. If there are more fast-twitch movement units in the performed movement, the higher the movement speed is [9]. High-velocity exercise changes the ratio of fast-twitch and slow-twitch motor units. Speed is considered largely genetic. There are simple and complex forms of quickness. Simple quickness refers to simple reaction time, while complex quickness involves multi-step reaction patterns.

The speed-strength qualities of movement technique development depend on the level of tension of certain muscles and their contraction, in which it should not differ more than 10% from competitive work. In such conditions, intermuscular coordination develops to the maximum extent, which corresponds to the development of coordinated movements with neither maximum nor minimum tension. Two main tasks must be solved in the development of speed and strength (to be addressed):

1. To increase the set of speed power options.
2. To develop of the ability to master these qualities.

To solve the first task, exercises of local and regional importance should be used. The number of loads used in these exercises should be repeated from one to 8-10 times [7].

The second task is performed by using special regional and global exercises, where the resistance is equal to the resistance in the competition, and the speed should be maximum. The main method is swinging, in which a quarter of the exercises should be relaxed and performed in isometric mode. Speed strength training, especially sudden bursts of exercise, is associated with features such as exertion and breath holding. Within a short time of movements, it creates characteristic vegetative reactions of high power.

Agility is the ability to solve a given movement task quickly, purposefully and resourcefully. The development of the quality of agility is closely related to the development of strength and speed, because the level of strength of the athlete's agility plays an important role in performing any movement with agility. At the same time, the physiological mechanism of the quality of agility is much more complicated than the mechanism of other physical qualities, and it is not related to the speed of a certain ordinary reaction, but the speed of coordination of the work of several physiological systems with the speed of the transmission of nervous processes. The quality of agility depends on a person's age. As a person ages, the quality of agility tends to decrease.

The importance of the function of sensory systems in the emergence of agility [8]. In sports activities, especially in competitions held in sports that depend on the situation, the athlete's agility depends largely on how quickly they analyze information through sensory systems. The faster the situation is detected, the quicker an appropriate reaction can be formed. It is known that almost 90% of information from the environment is analyzed by the visual system, and the rest comes from other sensory systems.

Flexibility is a morphological and functional characteristic of the musculoskeletal system, which determines the amplitude of movement. Therefore, flexibility is a measure of the amplitude of motion. Flexibility is divided into two types: active and passive [10].

Active flexibility means the maximum amplitude of movement that a person can independently create without external assistance. The mobility of the joints is of great importance in the occurrence of such flexibility. That is, the more mobile the joint, the higher the elasticity, and the greater the amplitude of movement.

Passive flexibility is the range of motion in the joints that is achieved with the help of sports equipment or an athlete's partner or coach. Passive flexibility tends to be higher than active flexibility.

Endurance - a person's endurance during exercise is his ability to work for a long time without slowing down. Endurance depends on the functional reserves of the body, the level of physical fitness, and the important conditions in which the work is performed. Regularly engaging in special exercises increases the body's resistance to these activities [7].

Conclusion/Recommendations. It should be emphasized that training aimed at the development of one quality of the athlete may create a physiological and biochemical basis for the development of other qualities, but these additional effects are insufficient to achieve high sports results. The main conclusion comes from this, that is, any exercise in any type of sport should be

based on comprehensive general physical training, and based on this, it is necessary to develop the quality of leading (managing) importance for the given type of sport.

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